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Self-awareness and Workplace Harmony of Printing Companies in Port Harcourt, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between self-awareness and workplace harmony in printing companies in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Specifically, it explores how self-awareness influences two key measures of workplace harmony: goal attainment and cohesiveness. Drawing from the baseline theory, the study posits that self-awareness is crucial for managing stress, responding constructively to feedback, and fostering positive team dynamics, all of which contribute to a harmonious work environment. A cross-sectional survey research design was employed, with data collected from 62 staff members across 19 printing companies using a structured questionnaire. The reliability of the instrument was confirmed with Cronbach's Alpha, and hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS 23.0. The findings revealed significant positive relationships between self-awareness, goal attainment ($r = 0.727, p < 0.05$), and cohesiveness ($r = 0.581, p < 0.05$), underscoring the role of self-awareness in fostering workplace harmony. Based on these findings, the study recommends that organizations invest in emotional intelligence training to enhance self-awareness among employees, which could lead to improved performance, better team relationships, and a more harmonious workplace environment. These insights provide valuable implications for leadership development and organizational growth in the printing industry.

Keywords: Self-awareness, workplace harmony, goal attainment, cohesiveness, emotional intelligence, printing companies, Port Harcourt

INTRODUCTION

Workplace harmony is an essential component of organizational success, as it fosters a collaborative environment, reduces conflicts, and promotes the efficient attainment of organizational goals (Robbins & Judge, 2013). A harmonious workplace enables employees to work together effectively, contributing to improved productivity, job satisfaction, and overall organizational performance (George & Jones, 2008). In dynamic industries like printing, where collaboration, creativity, and

meeting client expectations are crucial, fostering workplace harmony becomes even more important to ensure seamless operations and timely project completion.

Self-awareness, a fundamental aspect of emotional intelligence, plays a critical role in achieving workplace harmony. According to Goleman (1995), self-awareness refers to the ability to recognize and understand one's emotions, thoughts, and behaviors and how they influence others. Individuals who possess high levels of self-awareness are better equipped to manage interpersonal relationships, regulate emotions, and make decisions that align with their values. In the context of organizational settings, self-awareness is linked to better communication, enhanced leadership skills, and improved conflict resolution (Kabat-Zinn, 2005). These qualities are vital for promoting harmony in the workplace, particularly in industries where teamwork and cohesion are key.

In the printing industry, which involves a high degree of collaboration between designers, production teams, and client-facing roles, self-awareness becomes a critical attribute for managing relationships and ensuring smooth interactions. Employees who are self-aware are more likely to understand the impact of their actions on others, adjust their behavior based on feedback, and foster an inclusive and respectful work environment. This, in turn, can lead to improved goal attainment and cohesiveness within teams, which are essential aspects of workplace harmony (Eurich, 2018). Previous studies have demonstrated that self-awareness is positively associated with emotional regulation, which helps reduce stress and conflict in the workplace, thus promoting harmony (Cherniss & Goleman, 2001).

Despite the increasing recognition of the importance of emotional intelligence and self-awareness in organizational success, limited empirical research has been conducted on the relationship between self-awareness and workplace harmony, particularly in the printing industry in Nigeria. Most existing studies have focused on larger sectors such as manufacturing and services, leaving a gap in understanding how self-awareness influences workplace dynamics in more niche industries like printing. This study, therefore, aims to bridge this gap by examining the relationship between self-awareness and workplace harmony in printing companies in Port Harcourt.

The relevance of this study is underscored by the need for printing companies to maintain a harmonious work environment to meet client demands, enhance team performance, and remain competitive in the market. By understanding the impact of self-awareness on goal attainment and cohesiveness, this research will provide valuable insights for managers and leaders in the printing industry to foster a more harmonious and productive workplace.

1. To ascertain the relationship between self-awareness and goal attainment in printing Companies in Port Harcourt.
2. To examine the relationship between self-awareness and cohesiveness in printing Companies in Port Harcourt.

Based on the above objectives, the study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the relationship between self-awareness and goal attainment in printing Companies in Port Harcourt?
2. What is the relationship between self-awareness and cohesiveness in printing Companies in Port Harcourt?

The conceptual framework showing the relationship between self-awareness and workplace harmony is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Self-awareness and Workplace harmony.
Source: Desk Research, 2024.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, also known as the Motivation-Hygiene Theory, focuses on the factors that lead to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. According to Herzberg, job satisfaction is influenced by motivating factors, while dissatisfaction is primarily caused by hygiene factors. Understanding this theory in the context of self-awareness and workplace harmony can provide insight into fostering a more harmonious and productive environment. When employees are self-aware, they can better understand the motivators and hygiene factors that influence their own job satisfaction and performance. Herzberg (1966) emphasized that motivators, such as achievement, recognition, and responsibility, are linked to positive job experiences and personal growth. Self-aware employees are more likely to seek roles and tasks that align with their intrinsic motivators, contributing to personal fulfillment and increased engagement.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory helps illuminate how achieving workplace harmony depends on addressing both motivators and hygiene factors. For instance, when employers focus solely on improving hygiene factors such as ensuring competitive salaries and safe working conditions without paying attention to motivators, the workplace may not foster long-term harmony (Herzberg, 1966). While employees may not be dissatisfied, they may also not feel motivated to contribute to a cohesive and harmonious work environment. In contrast, focusing on motivators such as providing opportunities for personal development, recognizing individual contributions, and fostering a sense of achievement can create a more harmonious workplace (Herzberg, 1966). Employees who feel motivated and appreciated are more likely to exhibit positive behaviors, such as collaboration and support for their colleagues, which in turn promotes workplace harmony. Moreover, self-awareness among employees enhances this process, as individuals who understand their personal motivators and hygiene factors can better contribute to a positive, balanced work culture.

The Concept of Self-Awareness

Self-awareness refers to the ability to consciously recognize and understand one's emotions, thoughts, behaviors, and their impact on others. It is a fundamental aspect of emotional intelligence, playing a crucial role in both personal and professional development. According to Goleman (1995), self-awareness is essential for managing emotions and ensuring that actions align with one's values. Self-aware individuals tend to have a clearer understanding of their strengths and weaknesses, enabling them to set realistic goals and pursue continuous improvement. Self-awareness can be divided into

two dimensions: internal and external. Internal self-awareness involves a deep understanding of one's own emotions, values, and personality traits, helping individuals make decisions that are consistent with their core beliefs. External self-awareness, on the other hand, relates to recognizing how others perceive you. Eurich (2018) suggests that high external self-awareness fosters better relationships and enhances leadership qualities by making individuals more receptive to feedback, allowing them to adjust their behavior accordingly.

Self-awareness also has a significant impact on emotional regulation and resilience. When individuals are aware of their emotional triggers, they are better equipped to manage stress and respond to challenges in a calm, composed manner. This ability to regulate emotions is crucial for maintaining a stable mental state, which benefits both personal well-being and workplace productivity (Kabat-Zinn, 2005). Moreover, self-aware individuals tend to be more empathetic, recognizing and responding to the emotions of others more effectively. This is particularly important in team dynamics and leadership roles, where understanding others' perspectives can lead to improved communication and collaboration (Goleman, 1995).

Emotionally intelligent individuals maintain an awareness of the roles they play and the social labels associated with them (Averill, 1980). According to Scheff (1983), emotions are culturally specific, and individuals must interpret and appraise the cultural expectations for emotional displays, adjusting their behavior accordingly. Self-aware individuals understand these cultural roles and perform within the norms established by their communities, which helps in maintaining harmony and appropriate emotional expression. This self-awareness also guides individuals in setting priorities, allowing them to focus on pressing issues and set aside inconsequential problems (Abraham, 1999; George, 2000). This is especially applicable in workplace interactions, where a high level of self-awareness helps teams address crucial issues while sweeping aside minor conflicts. Emotionally intelligent leaders are adept at maintaining focus on key project issues, thus enhancing overall team performance.

The Concept of Workplace Harmony

Workplace harmony refers to a positive, cooperative, and productive environment where employees work collaboratively, respect each other, and contribute to the success of the organization. Achieving workplace harmony involves creating a culture that promotes open communication, mutual respect, and emotional well-being among employees. A harmonious workplace is essential for both individual and organizational performance, as it fosters engagement, satisfaction, and overall productivity (George & Jones, 1996). Several factors contribute to workplace harmony, including effective communication, emotional intelligence, leadership, and a supportive organizational culture. Open communication allows employees to express their ideas, concerns, and feedback without fear of retribution, which reduces misunderstandings and conflicts (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Furthermore, when employees feel heard and valued, they are more likely to collaborate effectively, promoting a sense of belonging and unity.

Emotional intelligence, particularly self-awareness and empathy, is another critical factor in achieving workplace harmony. Employees with high emotional intelligence are better able to manage their emotions and respond to others with empathy and understanding, which reduces interpersonal conflicts and enhances cooperation (Goleman, 1995). Leaders who exhibit emotional intelligence can foster a positive atmosphere by setting a tone of respect and fairness, which contributes to a cohesive and harmonious work environment (Mayer, Caruso, & Salovey, 2000).

A supportive organizational culture is essential for workplace harmony. Organizations that promote inclusivity, respect for diversity, and fairness tend to foster more harmonious relationships among employees (Schein, 2010). Such cultures encourage collaboration and discourage behaviors like discrimination, gossip, or hostility, which can disrupt workplace harmony. A culture that values psychological safety, where employees feel secure in taking risks and speaking up without fear of negative consequences, also promotes harmony and innovation (Edmondson, 1999). Workplace harmony is closely linked to employee satisfaction and retention. Employees who feel that they work in a harmonious environment are more likely to be engaged in their work, experience lower levels of stress, and remain loyal to the organization (Kouzes & Posner, 2007). A harmonious workplace also positively impacts teamwork, leading to better collaboration, increased innovation, and improved problem-solving capabilities (Tjosvold, 1998).

Goal Attainment

Goal attainment refers to the process of achieving specific objectives or targets that have been set by an individual, group, or organization. It is a critical aspect of personal and professional success, as it provides a framework for measuring progress and performance. Locke and Latham (2002) define goal attainment as the culmination of efforts directed toward reaching desired outcomes, which helps individuals and organizations stay focused and motivated. Whether in the context of personal development or organizational growth, goal attainment plays a pivotal role in driving success and fostering a sense of accomplishment. The process of goal attainment begins with goal setting, which involves identifying clear, specific, and measurable objectives. Locke and Latham (1990) emphasize that setting goals leads to enhanced performance, as it provides individuals with a clear direction and motivation. Goals that are specific and challenging, yet achievable, tend to produce higher levels of effort and persistence. When individuals and teams have well-defined goals, they are better equipped to allocate their time and resources effectively, leading to higher levels of productivity and performance.

Goal attainment, the process of achieving established objectives, is a key indicator of workplace harmony. A harmonious work environment fosters collaboration, effective communication, and alignment of efforts toward common goals, making it easier for teams and individuals to reach their targets (Locke & Latham, 2002). When workplace harmony is present, employees experience less conflict, higher levels of job satisfaction, and a greater sense of unity, all of which contribute to efficient goal attainment. Conversely, a disharmonious workplace can lead to confusion, miscommunication, and delays in achieving organizational goals. In harmonious workplaces, effective collaboration and communication play crucial roles in facilitating goal attainment. Open communication allows employees to share ideas, address challenges, and provide feedback in real-time, reducing the chances of misunderstandings and inefficiencies (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Moreover, when teams collaborate effectively, they pool their strengths and resources, increasing the likelihood of completing tasks and meeting goals on time (Tjosvold, 1998). This collective effort toward shared objectives is a strong indicator of workplace harmony, as it reflects the ability of employees to work together seamlessly.

Cohesiveness

Cohesiveness refers to the degree to which group members feel connected to one another and united in pursuing shared goals. It is a key factor in team dynamics, as it influences how effectively a group can work together to achieve common objectives. Cohesiveness can lead to enhanced collaboration, improved communication, and increased overall performance, making it a critical component of successful teams and organizations (Carron & Brawley, 2000). Groups that are cohesive tend to experience lower levels of conflict, higher satisfaction among members, and a stronger commitment to the group's goals. Cohesiveness is important in both small teams and large organizations because it fosters a sense of belonging and shared identity among members. According to Forsyth (2010), cohesiveness is built through regular interaction, mutual respect, and the perception of shared success. When team members feel connected and aligned with the group's goals, they are more likely to put forth extra effort, stay motivated, and maintain a positive attitude. This collective commitment can lead to better decision-making, creativity, and problem-solving, as members feel safe sharing ideas and taking risks (West, 2002).

Moreover, cohesive groups are better able to handle challenges and setbacks. Because members trust each other and are invested in the group's success, they are more likely to support one another during difficult times. This social support can reduce stress and improve the group's resilience, enabling them to navigate obstacles more effectively (Bennett & Naumann, 2005). Several factors contribute to the development of group cohesiveness. One key factor is group size; smaller groups tend to be more cohesive because members have more opportunities for interaction and relationship-building (Hackman, 2002). The clarity of group goals also plays a role in fostering cohesiveness. When goals are clear and mutually understood, members are more likely to align their efforts and work together toward achieving them (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Additionally, shared values and norms can strengthen cohesiveness, as they provide a common foundation for group behavior and decision-making.

Research has consistently shown that group cohesiveness is positively correlated with group performance. Groups that are cohesive tend to perform better because their members are more engaged and committed to the group's objectives (Mullen & Copper, 1994). High levels of cohesiveness also reduce absenteeism and turnover, as members are more satisfied with their roles and the group dynamic (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Additionally, cohesive groups are better able to coordinate their efforts and avoid duplication of work, leading to greater efficiency and productivity. Cohesiveness is a critical factor in the success of teams and organizations. It fosters collaboration, improves communication, and enhances overall performance. Groups that are cohesive are more likely to experience high levels of satisfaction and commitment among members, leading to better decision-making and problem-solving. By promoting regular communication, setting clear goals, and managing conflict effectively, organizations can build and maintain cohesive teams that thrive in achieving their objectives.

Empirical Review

Self-awareness, a core component of emotional intelligence, refers to the ability to recognize and understand one's emotions, thoughts, and behaviors, and how they affect others (Goleman, 1995). Workplace harmony, on the other hand, involves a state of positive interpersonal relationships, mutual respect, and a cooperative atmosphere that facilitates smooth interactions and effective collaboration among employees (Robbins & Judge, 2013). Empirical research suggests that self-awareness plays a significant role in promoting workplace harmony, as individuals who are more aware of their emotions and behaviors tend to foster more positive and productive relationships within their teams.

One key area in which self-awareness impacts workplace harmony is through emotional regulation. Research by Kabat-Zinn (2005) indicates that individuals with high self-awareness are better able to regulate their emotions, which in turn reduces conflicts and tensions in the workplace. For instance, people who are aware of their emotional triggers are more likely to manage stress and respond to challenging situations in a calm and composed manner, thereby minimizing the risk of interpersonal conflicts. These findings are supported by a study conducted by Cherniss and Goleman (2001), which found that emotionally intelligent individuals, particularly those with high self-awareness, were more adept at managing workplace tensions, resulting in greater interpersonal harmony and team cohesion. Self-awareness also enhances interpersonal relationships in the workplace, which is crucial for maintaining harmony. Eurich (2018) highlights that external self-awareness—understanding how others perceive you—helps individuals adjust their behavior based on feedback, leading to better communication and collaboration. In her study, Eurich found that employees who possessed high levels of self-awareness were more likely to engage in positive interpersonal behaviors, such as active listening and empathy, which reduced misunderstandings and facilitated harmonious working environments. Additionally, self-aware individuals tend to recognize the impact of their actions on others and are more likely to avoid behaviors that could lead to conflict or disharmony (Goleman, 1995).

A study by Jordan and Troth (2004) further supports the link between self-awareness and workplace harmony by examining the role of emotional intelligence in team dynamics. Their research revealed that teams with higher collective emotional intelligence, particularly self-awareness, experienced fewer conflicts and demonstrated higher levels of cooperation and collaboration. The researchers concluded that self-awareness is essential for building trust and mutual respect among team members, which are critical components of workplace harmony.

Leaders who possess high levels of self-awareness also contribute significantly to workplace harmony. Studies on transformational leadership indicate that self-aware leaders are better able to understand the needs and emotions of their team members, fostering an inclusive and harmonious work environment (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Research by Lanser (2000) demonstrated that leaders who practice self-awareness are more likely to communicate effectively, provide constructive feedback, and manage conflicts in a way that preserves harmony within the team. This was further supported by a study by Gardner et al. (2005), which found that self-aware leaders promote an atmosphere of trust and open communication, which enhances workplace harmony by preventing misunderstandings and fostering collaboration.

In team settings, self-awareness can improve group cohesion and cooperation, which are essential for workplace harmony. A study by Druskat and Wolff (2001) investigated how self-awareness affects group emotional intelligence and its impact on team performance and harmony. The findings revealed that teams composed of individuals with high levels of self-awareness were better at managing interpersonal relationships, which reduced conflict and improved team cohesion. The researchers concluded that self-awareness enables individuals to recognize and address tensions before they escalate into conflicts, thus maintaining a harmonious work environment. Furthermore, Bennett and Naumann (2005) explored the effects of group cohesiveness and self-awareness on team performance and harmony. Their study showed that self-awareness enhances group cohesion by encouraging members to engage in more cooperative behaviors and reducing tendencies toward destructive conflict. The authors argued that self-aware team members are more likely to prioritize group goals over individual differences, contributing to a more harmonious and productive work environment.

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Self-Awareness and Emotional Regulation

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Leadership, Self-Awareness, and Workplace Harmony

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Based on the foregoing, the following hypotheses are stated.

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between self-awareness and goal attainment in printing Companies in Port Harcourt.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between self-awareness and cohesiveness in printing Companies in Port Harcourt.

METHODOLOGY

For this study, a cross-sectional survey research design was chosen to investigate the relationships between self-awareness and various aspects of workplace harmony, including goal attainment, cohesiveness. This design allows for a thorough examination of how these variables interact with one another and provides insights into their associations. The study employed a quantitative methodology, which enables the measurement and analysis of relationships in numerical terms while also offering insights into the human elements behind the data. This approach provides a comprehensive understanding of how self-awareness impacts workplace harmony and allows for precise quantification of these relationships. The study's population consists was sixty-two (62) staff of 19 printing press companies in Port Harcourt. Data was collected using a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The questionnaire was designed to capture relevant information about self-awareness and workplace harmony aspects. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by the use of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items scoring above 0.70. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product moment Correlation with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 23.0. The tests were carried out at a 95% confidence interval and a 0.05 level of significance.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Table 1: Self-Awareness and Goal Attainment

		Correlations	
		SEFA4	GOLA4
SEFA4	Pearson Correlation	1	.727**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	57	57
GOLA4	Pearson Correlation	.727**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	57	57

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey data, 2024

The correlation table 1 above clearly demonstrates a positive relationship between self-regulation and goal attainment. The r value of 0.727 confirms this relationship, and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, based on empirical findings, the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between self-regulation and goal attainment.

Table 2: Self-Awareness and Cohesiveness

		Correlations	
		SEFA4	COHE4
SEFA4	Pearson Correlation	1	.581**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	57	57
COHE4	Pearson Correlation	.581**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	57	57

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey data, 2024

The correlation Table 2 above clearly demonstrates a positive relationship between self-regulation and cohesiveness. The r value of 0.581 confirms this relationship, and it is significant at $p\ 0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, based on empirical findings, the null hypothesis earlier stated is hereby rejected. Therefore, there is a significant relationship between self-regulation and cohesiveness.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study revealed significant relationships between self-awareness and various aspects of workplace harmony, specifically goal attainment and cohesiveness, in printing companies in Port Harcourt. This section discusses these findings in light of previous empirical research and theoretical frameworks. The study found a strong positive relationship between self-awareness and goal attainment, as evidenced by the correlation value of 0.727. This result is consistent with Goleman’s (1995) assertion that self-awareness, as a critical component of emotional intelligence, enhances an individual’s ability to align actions with personal and organizational goals. Employees who are self-aware are more likely to understand their strengths and weaknesses, enabling them to set realistic goals and pursue them effectively. This finding aligns with prior research by Cherniss and Goleman (2001), who emphasized that self-aware individuals have greater emotional regulation, which helps them remain focused and resilient in the face of challenges, thereby improving their goal achievement.

In the context of the printing industry, where deadlines and precision are crucial, self-awareness enables employees to manage their time effectively, communicate their needs, and seek assistance when necessary. This, in turn, fosters a culture of accountability and goal-oriented behavior, as self-aware employees are more likely to take ownership of their tasks and contribute to the collective success of the team. Thus, the positive correlation between self-awareness and goal attainment in this study supports the notion that self-awareness is essential for achieving organizational goals and maintaining productivity in high-pressure environments such as printing companies (Eurich, 2018).

The study also demonstrated a positive relationship between self-awareness and team cohesiveness, with a correlation value of 0.581. This finding suggests that self-awareness contributes significantly to creating harmonious working relationships within teams. According to Goleman (1995), self-awareness enhances an individual’s empathy and understanding of others’ emotions, which are crucial for fostering cooperation and reducing conflicts. In a team-oriented industry like printing, where collaboration between departments is essential for meeting client expectations, self-awareness enables employees to navigate interpersonal relationships more effectively.

The moderate correlation observed between self-awareness and cohesiveness supports the view that emotionally intelligent individuals, through heightened self-awareness, can better manage team dynamics. They are more open to feedback, willing to adjust their behavior, and capable of understanding how their actions impact others (Kabat-Zinn, 2005). This leads to improved communication, reduced misunderstandings, and stronger team bonds. Furthermore, emotionally self-aware leaders are likely to create a more inclusive and supportive work environment, which fosters team unity and a shared sense of purpose. This aligns with research by Lanser (2000), who argued that self-awareness is critical for enhancing leadership effectiveness and team cohesion.

The overall findings suggest that self-awareness plays a pivotal role in promoting workplace harmony. By enhancing goal attainment and cohesiveness, self-awareness contributes to a more harmonious and productive work environment. These findings resonate with the theoretical underpinnings of emotional intelligence, which posit that self-aware individuals are better equipped to handle workplace challenges and interpersonal relationships (George & Jones, 2008). In the printing industry, where team coordination and timely delivery are critical to success, fostering self-awareness among employees can lead to smoother operations and greater organizational harmony.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study has examined the relationship between self-awareness and workplace harmony in printing companies in Port Harcourt, specifically focusing on how self-awareness influences goal attainment and cohesiveness. The findings revealed significant positive relationships between self-awareness and both aspects of workplace harmony. These results emphasize the critical role self-awareness plays in fostering a harmonious work environment, particularly in industries like printing, where collaboration, communication, and goal-oriented behavior are essential for success. Employees with high self-awareness can better manage stress, respond constructively to feedback, and contribute positively to team dynamics, which enhances productivity and reduces conflicts. The significance of these findings lies in their practical implications for organizational effectiveness. By fostering self-awareness, organizations can create more harmonious work environments where employees are not only focused on achieving goals but also more attuned to team dynamics.

Given the significant relationships between self-awareness, goal attainment, and cohesiveness, it is recommended that organizations should consider investing in emotional intelligence training to enhance employees' self-awareness. This could lead to improved job performance, higher levels of employee satisfaction, and a more harmonious workplace environment.

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